

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines.

Marcelino F. Cuyab, Eugenio S. Guhao, Jr.

¹Student of Doctor in Philosophy of Management in University of Mindanao, Matina, Davao City, Philippines

¹Instructor II, Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology, Province of Davao del Norte, Philippines

²Dean of Professional Schools, University of Mindanao, Matina, Davao City, Philippines.

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to determine the best fit model of work engagement specifically; it established the interrelationship of service quality, decision-making, psychological empowerment among hotel employees in Region XI, Philippines. Quantitative research design and structural equation model (SEM) were utilized. The data were gathered from 408 hotel employee using the four sets of survey questionnaires. The exogenous variables are service quality, decision-making, psychological empowerment with endogenous variable of work engagement. Findings revealed that the level of service quality, psychological empowerment, and work engagement were very high, and high for decision-making. There was significant relationship between and among service quality, decision-making, psychological empowerment significantly influences work engagement. Model suggested that service quality and decision-making are drivers of work engagement. However, in the final analysis, psychological empowerment was not supported in the model fit. The model fit consisted of service quality and work engagement, decision-making and work engagement and between decision-making and service quality. The generated model 4 fits best anchored on work engagement indicating that the higher degree on the decision-making the greater service quality were provided of the hotel employees leading to intense degree of work engagement.

Keywords: *Decision-making, Psychological Empowerment, Service Quality, Work Engagement, Region XI, Philippines*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

The prevailing issues on work engagement such as unhappy, constantly complaining, making excuses, prevarication, no initiative, irresponsible, do not help others, and lack of enthusiasm are among the personal characteristics of disengaged employee they are likely tends to lose their commitment, creativity, productivity which resulted to the decrease in performance. Work engagement is a worldwide phenomenon. Indeed, research in Malaysia revealed serious issues associated with worker turnover this is the main reason for the employee to escape from a hostile environment (Walsh & Taylor 2007).

This study on work engagement is significant because this would help to assess the current condition of job engagement among hotel employees in Region XI. As observed, work-related problems like stress, withdrawal behavior among employees including but not limited to moral, and other situational factors are directly associated with work disengagement. The importance of work engagement is to understand the dissatisfaction of the employees on their job results in professional stagnation and might be dangerous. The most notable fact is employees are found contented equally in their work and lives. This implies that employees who are not engaged have no intimately emotional and personal attachment in their work (Crabb 2011; Niemiec 2017). Thus, this study filled the gap to those previous studies conducted since no study doings were covering all the same variables stated above in the Philippines particularly in the Region XI hotel industries. Similarly, this research study aimed to contribute to the overgrowing array of literature and the new model which consequently hoped to give a new development towards enhancement meaningful contribution to new knowledge.

1.2. Research Objectives

The main purpose of the study was to determine the appropriate model for work engagement among hotel employees and assess the level of service quality, decision-making, psychological empowerment, and work engagement. Determine the significant relationship among exogenous variables with endogenous variable. Finally, to determine the best fit model that predicts work engagement among hotel employees in region XI, Philippines.

1.3. Research Hypothesis

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. There was no significant relationship between service quality and work engagement, decision-making and work engagement, psychological empowerment and work engagement. There is no model that best fits work engagement among hotel employees in region XI, Philippines.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theories, concepts, and propositions relevant to this study are discussed in this section to provide a strong frame of reference about the variables under study. One of the exogenous variables of the study is service quality with the following indicators: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. Another exogenous variable is decision-making with the following indicators: thoroughness, control, hesitancy, social resistance, optimizing, hesitancy and instinctiveness. The last latent exogenous variable is psychological empowerment in terms of meaning, competence, self-determination and impact as the indicators. Oppositely, the endogenous variable of this study is work engagement with the following indicators: emotional engagement, rational identification, compatibility, team orientation and motivation (Kirsch 2000).

2.1. Service Quality. In the services marketing research, quality is the major consideration to gain and retain the satisfaction and the loyalty of the employees in an organization, since rendering effective and efficient service to the clients is the major goal of every organization. In a few decades, innovative procedures in evaluating service quality have become the major area in marketing literature. Since the growing necessity of services, researchers and business operators have been rendering on the effective and efficient services delivered. In fact, delivering quality service is considered to be an important strategy for success in today's competitive world, for both qualities of services must be rendered by the employees to give full satisfaction to the receivers of the services (Ramseook-Munhurrun 2010).

2.2. Decision-making. The work engagement explains the involvement of employees in all the decision-making processes like policy formation, changes in policies and the means of achieving its objectives. It is the system that encourages workers' participation to do the job in the thought process of selecting a logical choice from the available options (Richardson 2014). In support, effective and efficient decision-makers are cognizant of the necessity of identifying and determining the problem and understanding the situation (Kepner & Tregoe 2005).

2.3. Psychological Empowerment. Psychological empowerment has a relation to the personal convenience of the employees, has the confidence to perform their work effectively and being dedicated to the work environment. However, psychologically empowered employees have lower intentions to quit. Evidently, the study focuses on the four reasons for empowerment as possible conditions that will contribute to employee engagement. This means that the employee's work engagement is influenced by the supervisors empowering behavior that motivates them to be involved more with their work. (Meyerson & Kline 2008).

2.4. Work Engagement. Work engagement has emerged as a popular organizational concept in recent years. This becomes the top priority of human resource practitioners in the organization in the business world. The determinants of both success or failure of the organizations are largely dependent upon employees working in it, since the most important asset of the organization is the employees, yet it needs to have a better relationship (Khan 2013). Adding on, it has been emphasized in industry, academic studies, and public office operations. Wherefore, the values that will be derived from this work engagement have added considerably in the organization's goals achievements. However, despite the attention increases, there is insufficient empirical research on employee engagement which indicates that there is still a need for analyzing the influence of employee engagement in work (Saks 2006).

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This chapter dealt with the discussion of research methods and procedures employed by the researcher in this study; these include the research design, research locale, population and sample, research instruments, data gathering procedure and statistical tool.

3.1. Research Design. This study utilized Structural Equation Model (SEM) method of research in which this method is a measure of association of variables with varying levels of measurement. The identified population examined the extent to which two or more variable relates to one another. The researcher also utilized the quantitative non-experimental design research method to determine the relationship of service quality and work engagement, decision-making and work engagement, and psychological empowerment and work engagement among the hotel employees of Region XI.

3.2. Research Locale. The study was conducted in Davao Region, designated as Region XI, one of the regions in the Philippines situated in the southern portion of Mindanao. The respondents of this study came from the component cities in Region XI namely: Tagum City, Davao City, Digos City, Mati City, and Panabo City in which considered the center of trade and commerce. Moreover, the researcher acquired the assistance of the various hotel administrations and duly asked for their permission to conduct study in order to reach the respondents.

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

3.3. Population and Sample. This study aimed to assess the work engagement among the Hotel Employee in Region XI which had been selected using stratified random sampling to highlight differences between groups in a population as the respondents of this study. It involved 400 hotel employees designated in different hotel establishments in the region with the following pre-inclusion criteria: at least ages 18 and above and with the length of service at least six months; and could be in managerial or non-managerial position. Employees under or beyond the stated criteria were excluded in this study, as well as those hotel establishments who declined the letter of permission to conduct the study. Moreover, by any circumstances that the qualified respondents had withdrawn his consent of participation would be any time allowed. The completed survey reached 408 which were higher than the maximum number of sample size which is 400.

3.4. Research Instrument. The survey questionnaires utilized in the conduct of the study were sourced from various related researches. Restructuring was carried out to make the instrument more contemporary. After the validation, pilot testing was conducted with the questionnaires obtaining Cronbach alpha of .916. It was articulated by Gliem (2003), that Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient normally ranges between 0 and 1. However, there is actually no lower limit to the coefficient. The closer Cronbach's alpha coefficient is to 1.0 the greater the internal consistency of the items in the scale, the following rule of thumbs were observed: Cronbach's Alpha > .9 - Excellent; Cronbach's Alpha > .8 - Good; Cronbach's Alpha > .7 - Acceptable; Cronbach's Alpha > .6 - Questionable; Cronbach's > .5 - Poor; and Cronbach's Alpha < .5 - unacceptable.

3.5. Statistical Tools. The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and testing the hypotheses **Mean.** This was used to determine the level of between work engagement, service quality, decision-making, and psychological empowerment. **Person Product Moment Correlation.** This was employed to determine the interrelationship between servant leadership between work engagement, service quality, decision-making, psychological empowerment. **Structural Equation Modelling.** This was utilized to explore the best fit model. The essence of the test according to Savalei and Bentler (2006) is to ensure the elimination of attributes with low correlations with the attributes of the other latent factors in the final SEM analysis.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Introduced in this chapter are the data and deconstruction of findings and results on the perception of causal model on the work engagement, service quality, and decision-making and psychological empowerment factors. Analyses and interpretation of data were made in the order of the objectives of the study posed earlier.

Table 1. Level of Service Quality

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Reliability	0.449	4.47	Very High
Responsiveness	0.459	4.53	Very High
Assurance	0.432	4.44	Very High
Empathy	0.431	4.44	Very High
Tangibles	0.558	4.13	High
Overall	0.347	4.40	Very High

Shown in table 1 is the level of service quality of hotel employees in Region XI with mean ranging from 4.13 to 4.53 with corresponding overall mean of 4.40 described as Very High with standard deviation of 0.347. This means that the service quality is always observed by the respondents. The rest of the indicators are organized from highest to lowest mean rating with their respective descriptive interpretation. For instance, responsiveness obtained a mean rating of 4.53 or Very High; reliability attained a mean rating of 4.47 or Very high; assurance and empathy got the mean of 4.44 equally, or Very High; tangibles obtained a mean of 4.13 or High. The overall Very High responses of hotel employees mean that the domain of service quality is always observed most of the time.

Table 2. Level of Decision-making

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Thoroughness	0.598	4.01	High
Control	0.568	3.87	High

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

Hesitancy	0.653	4.00	High
Social Resistance	0.541	4.17	High
Optimizing	0.590	3.90	High
Principled	0.743	3.91	High
Instinctiveness	0.811	3.54	High
Overall	0.421	3.91	High

Depicted in Table 2 is the level of decision-making of hotel employees. The means ranging from 3.54 to 4.17 with an overall mean rating of 3.91 with standard deviation of 0.421 described as High which means that the service quality is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

Table 3. Level of Psychological Empowerment

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Meaning	0.510	4.53	Very High
Competence	0.491	4.47	Very High
Self-Determination	0.531	4.27	Very High
Impact	0.656	4.22	Very High
Overall	0.427	4.37	Very High

Appended in Table 3 highlights the level of psychological empowerment had means ranging from 4.22 to 4.53 with an overall mean rating of 4.37 with standard deviation of 0.427 described as Very High, which means that the psychological empowerment is always observed by the respondents. The data for this indicators is consolidated from highest to lowest mean ratings as follows: meaning earned a mean rating of 4.53 or Very High; competence garnered a mean rating of 4.47 or very High; self-determination obtained a mean rating of 4.27 or Very High; impact has a mean rating of 4.22 or Very High for giving meaning towards individual task.

Table 4. Level of Work Engagement

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotional Engagement	0.533	4.32	Very High
Rational Identification	0.508	4.36	Very High
Compatibility	0.620	4.08	High
Team Orientation	0.384	4.32	Very High
Motivation	0.432	4.57	Very High
Overall	0.400	4.33	Very High

Indicated in Table 4 highlight the level of work engagement had a mean ranging from 4.08 to 4.57 with an overall mean rating of 4.33 with standard deviation of 0.400, described as Very High, which means that work engagement is always observed by the respondents. The mean ratings of the indicators of work engagement are arranged from highest to lowest mean rating as follows: motivation obtained a mean rating of 4.57 or Very high; rational identification acquired a mean rating of 4.36 or Very High; emotional engagement has a mean rating of 4.32 or Very High; team orientation attained a mean rating of 4.32 or very High; compatibility garnered a mean rating of 4.08 or High for having feel connected with the company whom they work.

Table 5. Correlations between Service Quality and Work Engagement

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

Service Quality	Work Engagement					Overall Work Engagement
	Emotional Engagement	Rational Identification	Compatibility	Team Orientation	Motivation	
Reliability	.435* (.000)	.509* (.000)	.348* (.000)	.557* (.000)	.494* (.000)	.567* (.000)
Responsiveness	.545* (.000)	.462* (.000)	.396* (.000)	.517* (.000)	.549* (.000)	.604* (.000)
Assurance	.364* (.000)	.448* (.000)	.220* (.000)	.439* (.000)	.293* (.000)	.427* (.000)
Empathy	.188* (.000)	.411* (.000)	.090 (.068)	.374* (.000)	.165* (.001)	.290* (.000)
Tangibles	.193* (.000)	.359* (.000)	.284* (.000)	.313* (.000)	.195* (.000)	.333* (.000)
Overall Service Quality	.457* (.000)	.584* (.000)	.364* (.000)	.584* (.000)	.450* (.000)	.593* (.000)

Table 5 displays the data on the result of the relationship between service quality and work engagement. The overall r-value of 0.593 and equivalent probability value of .000 very much lower than .05 level of significant set in this study. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected in favor to the alternative hypothesis that there is significant relationship between service quality and work engagement. This means that high service quality high in work engagement. Analyzing further, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles as indicators of service quality when correlated to emotional engagement, got the overall r-value of 0.457 and p-value of .000 hence, insignificant. When the indicators of service quality were correlated to rational identification, the overall r-value is 0.584 p-value of .000 hence, accepting the null hypothesis of significant

Table 6. Correlation between Decision Making and Work Engagement

Psychological Empowerment	Work Engagement					Overall Work Engagement
	Emotional Engagement	Rational Identification	Compatibility	Team Orientation	Motivation	
Meaning	.387* (.000)	.351* (.000)	.365* (.000)	.400* (.000)	.475* (.000)	.486* (.000)
Competence	.506* (.000)	.544* (.000)	.404* (.000)	.543* (.000)	.611* (.000)	.635* (.000)
Self-Determination	.274* (.000)	.364* (.000)	.505* (.000)	.481* (.000)	.325* (.000)	.485* (.000)
Impact	.527* (.000)	.387* (.000)	.605* (.000)	.433* (.000)	.477* (.000)	.613* (.000)
Overall Psychological Empowerment	.549* (.000)	.524* (.000)	.615* (.000)	.592* (.000)	.602* (.000)	.714* (.000)

Table 6 shows data on the results of correlation between decision-making and work engagement. The overall obtained r-value is 0.452 and p-value of .000 very much lower than .05 level of significance of this study. It is therefore stated that hotel employees provide significant bearing that in every increases decision-making it will also increases work engagement. Moreover, it was observed that the thoroughness, control, hesitancy, social resistance, optimizing, principled, instinctiveness as indicators of decision-making when correlated to emotional engagement, the overall r-value is 0.323 and p-value of .000; thus, rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship. When indicators of decision-making correlated to rational identification, it obtained r-value of 0.356 and p-value of .000; hence, rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship. When indicators of decision-making correlated to compatibility garnered r-value of 0.474 and p-value of .000, it means that the null hypothesis is rejected. When indicators of decision-making correlated to team orientation, the r-value obtained 0.387 and p-value of .000; thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. When indicators of decision-making correlated to motivation, it earned r-value of 0.251 and p-value of .000; thus, rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

Table 7. Correlations between Psychological Empowerment and Work Engagement

Decision Making	Work Engagement					Overall Work Engagement
	Emotional Engagement	Rational Identification	Compatibility	Team Orientation	Motivation	
Thoroughness	.190* (.000)	.263* (.000)	.245* (.000)	.218* (.000)	.100* (.043)	.257* (.000)
Control	.153* (.002)	.340* (0.000)	.270* (.000)	.301* (.000)	.158* (0.001)	0.303* (.000)
Hesitancy	.378* (.000)	.290* (.000)	.559* (.000)	.269* (.000)	.310* (.000)	.467* (.000)
Social Resistance	.241* (.000)	.343* (.000)	.192* (.000)	.254* (.0000)	.143* (.004)	.291* (.000)
Optimizing	.322* (.000)	.262* (.000)	.307* (.000)	.201* (.000)	.169* (.001)	.323* (.000)
Principled	.176* (.000)	.043 (.388)	.241* (.000)	.287* (.000)	.113* (.023)	.212* (.000)
Instinctiveness	.067 (.179)	.172* (.000)	.330* (.000)	.239* (.000)	.157* (.002)	.244* (.000)
Overall Decision Making	.323* (.000)	.356* (.000)	.474* (.000)	.387* (.000)	.251* (.000)	.452* (.000)

Presented in Table 7 is the result of correlation between psychological empowerment and work engagement. The overall r-value is 0.714 and p-value of .000 which much lower than .05 level of significance set in this study. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted and signifies further that in every psychological empowerment support increases there is also a corresponding increase in work engagement. Articulating the details of the data, it was observed that meaning, competence, self-determination, impact as indicators of psychological empowerment when correlated to emotional engagement, the overall r-value is 0.549 and p-value of .000; hence, significant. When indicators of psychological empowerment were correlated to rational identification, the overall r-value is 0.524 and p-value of .000; thus, significant. When indicators of psychological empowerment correlated to compatibility, the overall r-value is 0.615 and p-value of .000; hence, significant. When the indicators of psychological empowerment correlated with team orientation, the overall r-value is 0.592 and p-value of .000; thus, significant. When the indicators of psychological empowerment correlated to motivation, the overall r-value of 0.602 and p-value of .000; which is significant and therefore accepting the null hypothesis.

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

Figure 6. Best Fit Model for Work Engagement

Legend:

- | | | |
|------------------------------|----------------------|----------------------|
| WE – Work Engagement | SQ – Service Quality | DM – decision-making |
| EE – Emotional Engagement | REL – Reliability | TH – Thoroughness |
| RI – Rational Identification | ASS - Assurance | |

Best Fit Model of Work Engagement

This section highlights the analysis on the interrelationship among service quality, decision-making, psychological empowerment to the work engagement of hotel employees in region XI. There are four alternative models tested to achieve best fit model of work engagement. Each model has a framework that could be decomposed into two sub-models which are the measurement model and structural model. The measurement model represents the measure loads on each factor to their latent constructs while structural model defines relations among the latent variables. Making it clearer, the assessment of fit was used as baseline for accepting and rejecting the model. As a rule, the researcher establishes the relationship of the causality of the latent variable toward the different latent variables. Furthermore, it institutes the relationship between endogenous and exogenous variables with the suitable fit, it underscores that there is consistency of empirical relationship among variables inferred by the model. The model parameter estimates entail the magnitude and direction among variables presented.

It could also be seen from the model that only emotional engagement and rational identification remained as the measurement construct of work engagement, out from five indicators. Emotional engagement, an observed variable that predicts work engagement, involves interest, boredom, happiness, anxiety, and other affective states. Any of three factors could affect employees' involvement with learning or their sustained effort in the workplace (Westerman & Simmons 2007). Another indicator of work engagement is rational identification. This pertains to clear understanding of the company's goals and objectives in relation to the role. According to Fernandez-Huerga (2008) rational choice theory then assumes that every individual, especially as part of the organization has his or her own preference among the available presented choices that allow them to display and perform what is the result of their choices.

For service quality, as one of the remaining exogenous variables in the best fit model, only two out of five observed variables appeared to have causal link to work engagement. Reliability said to have quality of being trustworthy or of performing consistently well. The rendered services resulted to dissatisfaction and satisfaction of the customers, and service provider must perform what have been promised to the clients. It is pivotal to make customers trust that the service provider is trustworthy to perform what it promises to do (Omar, Saadan & Seman 2015). Moreover, assurance is another indicator of service quality which predicted work engagement. It is an impulse to dwell on the required knowledge to answer customers' questions. This includes the steps that the service providers took to prevent problems, and truly understood the customers. This helps the quality service to be provided, increase efficiency and reduce wasteful spending (Alton 2017).

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

The only indicator of decision-making is thoroughness as a significant predictor of work engagement. In fact, doing work out all the pros and cons before making a decision were included in the model of thoroughness, of information search. Typical results showed that older adults used less information than younger or middle-aged adults. In this analysis, no significant age differences in thoroughness emerged. Also, in making decisions, thoroughness was contributed when selectivity is present in the choices. This is uniquely manifested to the variance in making quality of decision (Johnson 2011).

Table 8. Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures

Model	CMIN/DF 0<value>2	P-Value > .05	NFI > .95	TLI > .95	CFI > .95	GFI > .95	RMSEA < .05	P-Close > .05
1	8.616	.000	.672	.654	.696	.726	.137	.000
2	7.737	.000	.786	.749	.807	.852	.129	.000
3	7.504	.000	.876	.827	.907	.939	.126	.000
4	0.784	.503	.996	1.004	1.000	.998	.000	.807

Legend:

- CMIN/DF - Chi-Square/Degrees Freedom
- NFI - Normed Fit Index
- TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index
- CFI - Comparative Fit Index
- GFI - Goodness of Fit Index
- RMSEA - Root Means Square of Error
- P-close - P of Close Fit
- P-value - Probability Value

The generated structural model 4 in appended Figure 4 showing standardized solution is pictured out in Table 8 in summary of goodness fit. The results denote that the latent variables service quality representing the measured variables reliability, assurance and decision-making with measured variable in terms of thoroughness has significant contribution to the latent variable in terms of emotional engagement and rational identification and found to have correlation to each other. Presented in model 4, the chi-square divided by the degrees of freedom is 0.784 with the probability of 0.503. This indicates a very good fit of the model to the data. This is also strongly supported by RAMSEA index of 0.000 which is less than 0.05, with its corresponding p-close (0.807>0.05). Likewise, the other indices such as GFI (0.998>0.95), CFI (1.000>0.95), NFI (0.996>0.95), TLI (1.004>0.95). These indices satisfied the requirement of the goodness of fit measures. Moreover, this is an indication that generated model 4 is a very good fit model.

4. CONCLUSION

Conclusion

In the light of the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn. The respondents perceived that the level of work engagement is very high, which means that the hotel employees have engagement in their work based on the following level of measurement. The respondents manifest a very high level of emotional engagement and rational identification, which means that work engagement is always observed by the respondents. A very high level of reliability and assurance of service quality is also found out. This only implies that the service quality of hotel employees in Region XI is always observed. The result of thoroughness of decision-making as to influence is high, which means that the decision-making of hotel employees is oftentimes observed. Importantly, it is concluded that model 4 is the best fit model that predicts work engagement. The remaining indicators of work engagement are the following: compatibility, team orientation, and motivation which contributed the overall result. Finally, the results show a positive relationship as work engagement was correlated to psychological empowerment, service quality, and decision-making.

5. Acknowledgements

The researcher expresses his profound gratitude appreciation to the following people has contributed greatly in the accomplishment of this study. To Dr. Eugenio S. Guhao Jr, his adviser in this scholarly pursuit, for setting the right path that gave him the opportunity to prove his capacity as a researcher; Dr. Vicente Salvador E. Montano, the Chair of the dissertation committee and members: Dr. Myrna S. Viado, Dr. Stilo Floyd M. Schneider, Dr. Gaudencio G. Abellanosa, and Dr. Ana Helena R. Lovitos, Dr. Dan O. Gomez, the editor of this manuscript. For their significant suggestions and brilliant ideas, expertise and exemplary skills that made this work a reality.

The hotel managers, HR personnel's, and employees in Region XI for allowing the researcher to conduct this study in their respective hotels. His colleagues, co-researchers for their encouragement and moral support that served as a strong motivation for the researcher to go on this academic pursuit. His family, to whom he lovingly dedicates this endeavor, to his loving wives who are in heaven, Shella and Mae Jane, and mother, Margarita F. Cuyab, ever loved daughter Shynne and Alteah for their immeasurable understanding and love. Above all, to Almighty Father, for his manifold blessings, grace and sustenance that enables the researcher to reach the point of success. Thank you so much, Lord.

M.F.C

REFERENCES

- [1]. Alton, L. (2017), *Using quality assurance to improve your customer service*. Retrieved From <https://customerthink.com/using-quality-assurance-to-omprove-your-cutomer-service>
- [2]. Crabb, S. (2011), The use of coaching principles to foster employee engagement, *The Coaching Psychologist*, 7 (1), pp. 27-34.
- [3]. Fernandez-Huerga, E. (2008), The economic behavior of human beings: The Institutional/Post Keynesian model. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 4-(3):709-726.
- [4]. Gliem, R. (2003), *Calculating, interpreting, and reporting Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for Likert-type scales*. Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing, and Community Education.
- [5]. Johnson, M. (2011), Age differences in decision making: a process methodology for examining strategic information processing', *Journals of Gerontology*, vol. 45, no. 2pp. P75-P78, 1990.
- [6]. Kepner, C & Tregoe, B. (2005), 'Age differences in everyday problem-solving and decision-making effectiveness: a meta-analytic review', *Psychology and Aging*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 85-99, 2005.
- [7].Khan, E. (2013), 'Sense of relatedness as a factor in children's academic engagement and performance', *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 95(1), 148-162.
- [8]. Kirsch, C. (2000), *What is 'employee engagement'? Analysis of the factor structure of the engagement construct*. Change tracking research CTRE.
- [9]. Meyerson, S. & Kline, T. (2008), Psychological and environmental empowerment: antecedents and consequences, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 29, No. 5, pp. 444-460, 2008.
- [10]. Omar, H., Saadan, K. & Seman, K. (2015), 'Determining the influence of the reliability of service quality on customer satisfaction: The case of Libyan E-commerce customers', *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 5(1), 86-89.
- [11]. Ramseook-Munhurrun, P. (2010), 'Paternalistic leadership and subordinate responses: Establishing a quality service leadership model in Chinese Organizations. *Asian. Journal of Social Psychology*. 2004 7(1): 89-117.

Structural Equation Model on Work Engagement Among Hotel Employees in Region XI, Philippines

- [12]. Richardson, S. (2014), *New product development portfolios: Identifying the antecedents and consequences of decision-making processes*. TU Delft, Delft University of Technology.
- [13]. Saks, A. (2006), 'Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement', *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 21(7), 600–619.
- [14]. Savalei V. & Bentler, P. (2006), *Structural equation modeling*. In: Grover R, Vriens M, editors. *The handbook of marketing research: Uses, misuses, and future advances*. Sage; Thousand Oaks, CA: 2006. pp. 330–364.
- [15]. Walsh, B. & Taylor, S. (2007), 'The antecedents affecting employee engagement and organizational performance', *Asian Social Science*, 9(7), 41- 46.
- [16]. Westerman, J. & Simmons, B. (2007), 'The effects of work environment on the personality-performance relationship: An exploratory study', *Journal of Managerial Issues*. 19. 288-305.